

**THE EFFECT OF EXCHANGE RATE ON ECONOMIC GROWTH: A CASE STUDY
OF KENYA**

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DECLARATION

This project is our original work and has not been presented for a degree in any other university or institution

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ABSTRACT

Exchange rate policy and regimes do have a significant direct impact on economic growth. This paper intends to understand the effect of exchange rate on economic growth in Kenya. Real exchange rate devaluation is an expansionary effect there is evidence of very high degree of exchange rate pass-through to consumer prices would severely constrain such an option. For Kenya the need for maintain external competitiveness and promoting growth remains a delicate task for policymakers as it involves managing exchange rate regime accompanied by other consistent macroeconomic policies. The long debated subject of whether currency devaluation will positively affect economic growth or negatively was the statement problem of the research. The study aimed at determining the effect of exchange rate, inflation and foreign direct investment on economic growth. The study's theoretical base was built on International Fisher Effect Theory, Absolute and Relative purchasing power parity theories. The study utilized secondary data on the variables obtained from Central bank of Kenya official site, CEIC data site and macrotrend and it employed the descriptive research design. The study covered the period between 1993 and 2021 where the data was on annual basis. A linear multiple regression model was used as the model specification. The results indicated that the correlation between GDP and exchange rate is positive and strong, correlation between GDP and inflation is negative and strong and correlation between FDI and GDP is positive and fair. It indicated that 90.6 % of changes in the dependent variable GDP in this case are explained by the changes in the predictors that is; exchange rate, FDI and inflation rate. Individually all the predictors were found to be statistically significant and the coefficients indicated a p value of 0.000 for exchange rate, inflation rate and FDI. The study concluded that in deed exchange rate does have a positive impact on economic growth and that currency devaluations will influence economic growth positively. The study recommended that the Kenyan government should focus on implementing monetary trade policy that suit the Kenyan economy appropriately. It encouraged that exchange rate be managed more vigorously as it contributes well to economic growth. the study also acknowledged that maintaining a depreciated real exchange rate regime is going to be very complex.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

1. GDP: Gross Domestic Product
2. PPP: The purchasing power parity theory ppp
3. IFE: international fisher effect
4. FDI: Foreign direct investment
5. CBK: Central bank of Kenya
6. OLS: Ordinary Least Squares
7. ARDL: Autoregressive Distributed Lag Model
8. OCA: Optimal currency area
9. GMM: Generalized Method of Moments
10. CEIC: Census and Economic Information Center

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CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the study

The exchange rate can be defined as the conversion factor that determines the change of currencies in other words it tells you the value of your currency in another currency. It means how many units of one nation's currency can be purchased with one unit of domestic currency. (Musyoka, 2012)

It is a crucial topic in that its changes affect an economy by changing the cost of goods and services purchased from another country and also by changing the demand for their products from overseas.

When talking about exchange rate it is important to differentiate between nominal exchange rate and the real exchange rate. Real exchange rate is the exchange rate after inflation has been excluded while nominal exchange rate is when inflation is included. (Musyoka & Ocharo 2018)

There is volatility in real exchange rate which is essentially the short-term fluctuations of the real exchange rate. There are different patterns of exchange rate behavior and they are categorized into what is referred to as exchange rate regime. An exchange rate regime is a way a monetary authority of a country or currency union manages the currency about other currencies and the foreign

exchange market. The exchange rate regime in place at a particular time is linked to the monetary policy in place the exchange rate regimes include fixed exchange rate regime, purely floating exchange rate and managed exchange rate system. (Musyoka & Ocharo 2018)

Fixed exchange rate system is where the government fix the rate in that the rate at which one currency is converted to another remains fixed, purely floating is when exchange rates are completely flexible and move up and down due to changes in the factors influencing supply and demand. The rate is determined at the point where supply equals demand, managed exchange rate system on the other hand is where exchange rates are basically determined by the market forces but governments actively participate in the foreign exchange rate market and frequently intervene to buy or sell currencies or change the monetary policies to affect the exchange rate (Musyoka, & Ocharo). In a nutshell, a fixed exchange rate regime dictates that the domestic currency is dependent on another currency or other currencies while a floating exchange rate regime relies on the market that deals with the demand and supply of currencies (Ndavi, 2012). Between the two, there are intermediate regimes with various deviations of currency pegs. These regimes range from single currency, to crawling currencies to free floating currencies, which means the role of the monetary authority ranges from full control, to minimal control, to no control of the exchange rate. Countries report their exchange rate arrangements to the IMF during the Bretton Woods Institution conference in 1958, which publishes its regime classifications on the Annual Report on Exchange Arrangements and Exchange Restrictions (AREAER). The relationship between exchange rate and economic growth has been an important subject in economics as exchange rate regime and interest rates remain important issue of discourse in the internal finances as well as in developing nations where more economies have embraced trade liberations as a requisite for economic growth Dooley & Garber (2003) The exchange rate between two currencies is commonly determined by the

economic activity, market interest rates, gross domestic product and unemployment rate in each of the countries.

An increase in exchange rate means higher price of foreign exchange (domestic currency is relatively cheap) which means that there is depreciation, otherwise if there is a decrease in number of unit domestic currency needed to buy one unit of foreign exchange, then that is currency appreciation. (Musyoka & Ocharo 2012) The main objective of this study is to determine the effect of exchange rate on economic growth. The real effective exchange rate is a measure of the international competitiveness of an economy and an overvalued real exchange rate increases the price of domestic goods overseas or on other countries which eventually leads to a fall in demand for exports. Misalignment of the real exchange rate leads to price distortions and hence resource misallocation. Exchange rate is an important subject since it is an instrument to measure economic condition of the country, a country with a stable currency value translates stable economic conditions. Extremely high exchange rate fluctuations will disrupt economic activities in a country from both the real sector and the monetary sector. In pursuit for exchange rate stability, it is important to point out the factors that influence the movement.

Kenya's exchange rate has undergone various regime shifts since it gained independence in 1963. Economic events, especially balance of payment crises, have been the biggest cause of the regime shifts. The exchange rate was pegged to the US dollar until 1974 but the peg was changed to Special Drawing Rights (SDR) after discrete devaluations (Ndavi, 2012). SDR refer to an international type of monetary reserve currency created by the International Monetary Fund (IMF) in 1969 and it operated as a supplement to the existing money reserves of its members. The peg was changed to SDR because the movement in the nominal exchange rate in relation to the US

Dollar was unpredictable from 1974 to 1981 because of the oil price shocks, balance of payment problems and an increase in inflation.

The nominal exchange rate depreciated by 14% and this depreciation accelerated in 1981 and 1982 with further discrete devaluations. Between 1981 and 1982, the Kenyan shilling was devalued by about 20% in real terms measured against the Special Drawing Rights. After these devaluations, the exchange rate was changed to a crawling peg by the end of 1982. A crawling peg is a system of exchange rate adjustments in which a currency with a fixed exchange rate is allowed to fluctuate within a band of rates. (Ndavi 2012) This regime lasted until 1990 when a dual exchange rate was adopted and it lasted up to October 1993 when the exchange rate was fully liberalized. After a series of devaluations, the exchange rate was abolished, i.e., the official exchange rate merged with the market rate and the Kenyan shilling was allowed to float, determined in the market by the forces of demand and supply (Ndavi 2012). The objectives have been to maintain an exchange rate that would ensure international competitiveness while maintaining the domestic inflation rate at low levels, to conduct a strict monetary stance and also to sustain positive interest rates (Ndavi 2012). In the global economy economic trade with other countries is one of the important aspects of a country's economic development that has open economy the greater the interconnection between countries the more open the economy of the country.

This is reflected through increases of trade transaction and the flow of capital between the countries a country can fulfil its needs of obtain goods or services through import of said goods or services, a country may export the goods and services for countries in need of such services and goods. The regime of a country will have consequences on planning and implementation of macroeconomic policies including monetary policies. The reason behind this is because the greater the trade and financial transaction internally done by a country the greater the flow of foreign capital entering and leaving

the country concerned hence this flow of capital will affect the amount of money supply interest rate and exchange rate in the economy.

Example; In Nigeria exchange rate has change within the time frame from regulated to deregulated regimes. (Ewa2011) agreed that the exchange rate of naira was relatively stable between 1973 and 1979 [during the oil boom era and when agricultural products accounted for 70% of nation gross domestic product GDP (Mordi, 2006). But in 1986 when federal government adopted structural adjustment policy (SAP) the country moved from peg regime to a flexible exchange rate regime where exchange rate is left completely to be determined by market forces. Monetary forces may intervene periodically in the foreign exchange market in order to attain some strategic objectives (Mordi, 2006). However despite various efforts by government of Nigeria to maintain a stable exchange rate the naira has depreciated throughout the 1980's to date. As a result Nigeria economy have been forced to over depend on imports which have continued to slow economic growth. In Kenya exchange rate have been greatly impacted by inflation. Since the 1980's the rate of inflation has varied at times moving to double digits, where from late 1970's and from the 1980's the inflation was considered a serious problem to exchange rate since then the rate of inflation has risen tremendously which have led to continuous depreciation of exchange rate since early 1980's. The Kenya shillings was pegged to the sterling pound from 1966 then the peg was changed to the US dollar in 1971 and to the special drawing right SDR in 1975 in December 1982 the peg was changed to a standard basket of currencies and allowed to crawl in real terms this adoption of a crawling peg exchange rate in 1982 (Victor & Aliyu) compounded the inflation problem leading to exchange rate in Kenya depending on regime in operation (Mordi 2006).

By adopting a crawling peg exchange rate most researchers have argued the authorities decide to live with relatively high inflation where the rate of inflation and the exchange rate are closely

related with regime in operation. also, some researcher adoption of a crawling peg exchange rate may imply that the economy loses a nominal anchor that could control inflation and so the rate inflation could become uncontrollable reason be exchange rate and money supply are indirect to price level. Others argues that exchange rate and rate of inflation affect each other to product an inflation devaluation spiral or even a viscous circle in flexible exchange rate regime. This have led to the economy having to borrow from its trading partners like IMF in order to meet it demand for foreign currency .as a result the exchange rate of the Kenya shillings vs. others currencies like the dollar have continued to depreciates for the last 10 years. Kenya economy have continued to experience decline in it purchasing power which have slowed economic development.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

In many developing countries, Kenya being one of them, factors affecting economic growth have been a major topic of research. GDP Annual growth rate is averaged to be 4.83 percent from 2004 until 2021 (Central bank of Kenya 2022). Kenya has been struggling to maintain a stable growth throughout the years. Exchange rates have a huge potential in influencing the pace and direction of economic growth. There are many factors that influence a stable economic growth and among them is exchange rates. Khondker, Berisha and Razzaque (2012) believe that real devaluations have a positive effect on economic growth from a study conducted in Bangladesh while El-Ramly and Abdel-Halim (2013) believes that devaluations have negative effect on economic growth so there is contradictory evidence when it comes to effect of exchange rate on economic growth. This has been a very long debated subject in that is real devaluations good and positively affecting economic growth or is currency evaluation good and positive for the economy.

Different economists prefer currency depreciation whereas others prefer currency appreciation. Kenya, a developing country, has relatively thin financial markets and hence there is misalignment

of exchange rate, if it chooses a floating exchange rate then it is possible that the rate will be excessively volatile due to speculative reasons (Khondker, Berisha and Razzaque 2012). This means that there is a problem in choosing a regime which affects the depreciation or appreciation of the Kenyan currency. An increase in depreciation boosts economic growth as well as a decrease in appreciation (Khondker, Berisha and Razzaque (2012). However, this relationship holds for developing countries so that macroeconomic stability becomes one of their major economic development goals. Kenya exports primary products like tea, coffee, horticultural products, so many economists tend to dismiss the importance of exchange rate because developing countries majorly export primary products whose demand is essentially inelastic.

Alfred Marshall posited that in order for currency devaluation to have a positive impact on balance of trade, some of absolute price elasticity of exports and imports must be greater than basically, when considering a floating exchange rate regime, if the BOP is in disequilibrium, then the equilibrium will restore its balance without any government intervention. This, however, does not apply to least developed countries. The exchange rate should thus be maintained so as to avoid fluctuations and eventually bring about positive BOP. This will not only ensure Kenya is competitive in the global economy, but also improve living standards of the general public.

Again Ndavi (2012) pointed out that despite the importance of monetary policy and exchange rate policies in economic growth, few studies have been done in Kenya to determine the relationship as well as the exchange rate movements. Due to different conclusions from empirical studies, that is Khondker, Berisha and Razzaque (2012) believe that real devaluations have a positive effect on economic growth from a study conducted in Bangladesh while El-Ramly and Abdel-Halim (2013) believes that devaluations have negative effect on economic growth, Some economists believe that

overvaluation hurts economic growth while undervaluation facilitates it, while for most countries high growth periods are associated with undervalued currencies.

1.3 Research Objective

1.3.1 General objective

To determine the effect of exchange rates on economic growth rate in Kenya for the period 1993 to 2021

1.3.2 Specific objectives

1. To examine the effect of fluctuations of exchange rate on economic growth
3. To determine the effect of foreign direct investments on economic growth
4. To determine the effect of inflation rate on economic growth.

1.4 Research questions

1. How does fluctuations in exchange rates affect economic growth?
3. What is the effect of foreign direct investments on economic growth?
4. What is the effect of inflation on economic growth?

1.5 Scope of the study

The main objective of this research was to determine the effect of exchange rates fluctuations on economic growth. Question of interest was whether exchange rates do have a significant effect on economic growth. The study used time series data to analyze this effect of exchange rate on economic growth from 1993 to 2021.

1.6 Significance of the study

This research will benefit the government of Kenya in implementing an exchange rate regime that increases the GDP. This study is also meant to help the government to make better policies concerning the exchange rate. The exchange rate plays a key role in determining the price, which determines the demand for Kenyan export products on the world market. An increase in the exchange rate means that the Kenyan currency has depreciated, which will lead to higher demand for Kenyan exports in the world market. This however does not favor Kenya as a developing country because in reality, Kenya imports more goods than it exports therefore it ends up increasing the balance of payments deficit. A decrease in the exchange rate means that the Kenyan currency has appreciated, which means that Kenyan products become more expensive in the world market which lowers the demand, affecting the income received from the exports of goods and services. The research will benefit policy makers when coming up with policies regarding the exchange rate.

To scholars, academicians and other researchers, the findings of the study will help to bridge the existing empirical literature gap in that they will help show the effect of exchange rate on economic growth, a Kenyan case. This will therefore provide findings that can be compared to existing literature and thereby boost the accumulating empirical evidence on this area of academic inquiry. It will help explain theoretically and empirically how exchange rates do affect economic growth.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introductions

This chapter presents the review of literature on effect of exchange rate on economic growth. This is divided into theoretical as well as empirical literature review. The theoretical literature review presents theories that try to link exchange rates to economic growth including inherent limitations in the context of this study. Empirical literature review on the other hand presents the extant studies on this area. The empirical evidence is derived from both local studies as well as from studies around the globe. Subsequently, the conceptual framework and research gaps resulting from literature review are presented.

2.2 Theoretical framework

This section discusses the various theories that explain the relationship between exchange rates and economic growth.

2.2.1 The purchasing power parity theory (PPP)

The term Purchasing Power Theory was originated by Cassel in 1918. The PPP theory focuses on the inflation-exchange rate relationships and their impact on economic growth. According to Madura (2016) when a country's inflation rate rises relative to that of another country, decreased exports and increased imports depress the high inflation country's currency because of worsening trade and current account balances. The PPP theory attempts to quantify this inflation- exchange relationship.

The PPP theory relies on one key assumption and that is a basket of goods in one country should cost the same as an identical basket in another country. Madura (2016)

There are two forms of PPP theory: The absolute purchasing power parity and the relative purchasing power parity. The absolute form of PPP is an extension of the law of one price where it suggests that the prices of the same products in different countries should be equal when measured in common currency and on the other hand, the relative form of PPP accounts for market distortions like transport costs, labor costs, tariffs, taxes and quotas. It basically states that the rate of price changes should be similar. They are discussed in details below. . Madura (2016)

2.2.1.1 Absolute purchasing power parity.

The absolute PPP theory postulates that the equilibrium exchange rate between currencies of two countries is equal to the ratio of the price level in the two nations. Thus price of two similar products of two different countries should be equal when measured in a common currency as per the absolute version of PPP theory. Gustav Cassel, a Swedish economist popularized the PPP

theory during the time when countries like Germany, Hungary experienced hyperinflation and the purchasing power declined sharply hence affecting economic growth. The same currencies depreciated sharply against the stable currencies like the US dollar. . Madura (2016)

Using an example to understand the theory better, let P_a refer to the general price level in country A and P_b to denote general price level in country B, R_{ab} to the exchange rate between currency in country A and B. then the absolute purchasing power parity theory postulates that $R_{ab} = P_a/P_b$. This measure will show the impact exchange rate has on economic growth.

2.2.1.2 Relative purchasing power parity

The relative form PPP theory is an alternative version which postulates that the change in the exchange rate over a period of time should be proportional to the relative change in the price levels in the two nations over the same time period. This form of PPP theory accounts for market imperfections such as transportation costs, tariffs and quotas. Relative PPP theory accepts that because of market imperfections prices of similar products in different countries will not necessarily be the same when measured in a common currency. There are differences in tastes and preferences too. To be more specific it states that the rate of change in prices of products will be somewhat similar when currency measured in common as long as the trade barriers and transportation costs remain unchanged. The relative PPP theory often gives fairly good approximations of the equilibrium exchange rate and more so in periods of higher inflation. The PPP theory holds well over the very long run time period. . Madura (2016)

The PPP relationship can be simplified as $e_f = I_h - I_f$ when the inflation differential is small, where e_f is the exchange rate of the foreign country, I_f is the interest rate of the foreign country and I_h is the interest rate of the home country.

Numerical example is given below:

Suppose Interest rate for U.S is 9 % and UK is 5% then:

U.S consumers change in Price = Interest rates in the US = 9 % hence change in price in the U.K =
interest rate in the U.K + exchange rate in the U.K = 9%

For U.K consumers, change in Price in the U.K = Interest rate in the U.K = 5% hence change in
price in the U.S = Interest rate in the U.S – exchange rate in the UK

Figure 2.1: Graphical analysis of Purchasing Power Parity Theory.

Inflation rate differential (%)

2.2.2 International Fisher effect theory.

This theory was developed by Irving Fisher in 1930 Hatemi (2009). The international fisher effect (IFE) theory uses interest rates rather than inflation to explain the changes in exchange rate overtime and the impact on economic growth. The IFE closely related to the PPP because interest

rate are significantly correlated with inflation rates. The relationship between the percentage in the spot exchange rate over time and the differential between comparable interest rate in different countries capital markets is known as international fisher effect. Irving Fisher was a classical economist who made significant postulation about money supply and exchange rate and its impact on exchange rate. According to Hatemi (2009) The IFE suggests that given two countries the country with the higher interest rate will depreciate by the amount of the interest rate differential that is, within a country the nominal interest rate tend to approximately equal the real interest rate plus the expected inflation rate. Applied internationally, the IFE suggests that the nominal interest rate are unbiased indicators of future exchange rate. A country's nominal interest rate is usually defines as the risk free interest rate on a virtually costless loan. Risk free in the context means the risk faced other than inflation. The theory relied on the below assumptions: (Hatemi 2009)

- Capital flows freely between countries leading to equal interest rates worldwide.
- Real interest rates are equal between countries in the world
- No currency controls
- Capital markets are internationally integrated
- Differences in nominal interest rates between countries equals expected inflation.

It is often argued that an increase in a country's interest rate tend to increase the exchange value of its currency by inducing capital inflows which will increase economic growth. However the IFE argues that a rise in a country's nominal interest rates relative to the nominal interest rates of other countries indicate that the exchange value of the country's currency is expected to fall this is due to the increase in the country's expected inflation and not due to the increase in the nominal exchange rate. The IFE implies that if the nominal interest rate does not sufficiently increase to

maintain the real interest rate the exchange value of the country's currency tends to decline even further. Hatemi (2009)

The formula of the International Fisher Effect is as follows:

$$E = \frac{e_t}{e_0} - 1 = \frac{(i_d - i_f)}{(1 + i_f)} \dots \dots \text{equation 1}$$

$$\frac{E_t}{e_0} = \frac{(i_d - i_f)}{(1 + i_f)^t} + 1 = \frac{(i_d - i_f)}{(1 + i_f)^t} + \frac{(1 + i_f)^t}{(1 + i_f)^t} = \frac{(1 + i_d)^t}{(1 + i_f)^t} \dots \dots \text{Equation 2}$$

- Where E denotes percentage change in the exchange rates
- e_0 current spot exchange rate
- e_t spot exchange rate in the future
- i_d is domestic nominal interest rates
- i_f is foreign nominal exchange rates

Hatemi (2009)

2.2.3 Theoretical framework on inflation

Different economists have provided theories of inflation and are broadly categorized into two labels that is monetarists and structuralisms. Monetarists associated inflation with monetary causes and consequently suggested monetary measures to control it while structuralists believed that the inflation occurs because of imbalanced economic system and consequently suggested both monetary and fiscal measures to control the inflation. There are three main theories of inflation which include; market power theory of inflation, conventional demand-pull inflation and structural theories of inflation.

2.2.3.1 Market Power theory of inflation

This theory which was postulated by Prof Otto Eckstein theory is of the view that when a single group of sellers together decide a new price that is different from the competitive

price then the price is termed as market power price. Low rate of inflation causes long term economic growth. the groups responsible keep prices at level at which they can earn maximum profit which increases economic growth (Frisch 1983) The theory explains that while low rate of inflation affects economic growth positively high rate influences economic growth negatively for example in Kenya there has been immense high rate of inflation such that most low and middle income groups reduce consumption, which reduces aggregate demand hence decrease in economic growth. the theory goes ahead to explain an advanced version of the theory that oligopolists can increase the price to any level if the demand does not rise and the increase occurs because of increase in wages which further hikes inflation. (Frisch 1983)

2.2.3.2 Conventional demand pull inflation

According to this theory the only cause of inflation is excess aggregate demand over aggregate supply. In full employment equilibrium condition, when demand increases, inflation becomes unavoidable, the economy at this point is at maximum production capacity so this means that at this point supply cannot be increased further while the demand of products and services increase rapidly. Due to this imbalance between demand and supply inflation takes place in the economy. (Frisch 1983)

2.2.3.3 Structural theory of inflation

This theory was postulated by Myrdal and Straiten which believes that inflation occurs due to structural maladjustments in the economy. They are further categorized into two that is mark-up theory and bottle neck theory of inflation. (Frisch 1983)

- Mark-up theory

This theory was proposed by Prof Garner Ackley. According to him inflation cannot occur alone by demand and cost factors but by the cumulative effect of demand pull and cost push activities. This means that inflation occurs because of excess demand or increase in wage rate therefore both monetary and fiscal policies should be used to control inflation. (Frisch 1983)

- **Bottle neck inflation**

This theory was introduced by Prof Otto Eckstein. According to Prof Otto Eckstein the direct relationship between wages and prices is the main cause of inflation. In simpler words inflation takes place when there is a simultaneous increase in wages and prices of products. However, he believed that wage push or market power theories alone are not able to provide clear explanation of inflation. (Frisch 1983)

2.3 The conceptual framework

In terms of the study's conceptual framework, the independent variables will be exchange rate, inflation rate and foreign direct investment while the dependent variable is economic growth. The interrelationship between exchange rate and economic growth as shown in the figure below:

Figure 2.2:

The study will utilize monthly average period calculated annually. The data is obtained from Central Bank of Kenya site. Ndavi (2012), in the study of effect of exchange rate fluctuations on economic growth, utilized the data from the Central bank of Kenya site.

2.3.2: Inflation rate

Inflation rate is the rate of increase in prices over a given period of time. Inflation is typically a broad measure, such as the overall increase in prices or the increase in the cost of living in a country. The study will utilize annual inflation rate obtained from Central bank of Kenya site. Saungweme and Odhiambo 2012 also used annual inflation rate from Central bank of Kenya site.

2.3.3: Foreign direct investment

Is a category of cross-border investment in which an investor resident in one economy establishes a lasting interest in and a significant degree of influence over an enterprise resident in another economy (Duce and Espana 2003). The study will utilize foreign direct investments in US billion dollars obtained from macro trends site. Other researchers such as Ndavi (2012) also obtained the foreign direct investment figures from the macro trends site

2.3.4: Economic growth.

According to Arthur (2013), economic growth is An increase in the amount of goods and services produced per head of the population over a period of time (Arthur 2013), it can also be defined as an increase in aggregate production in an economy, which is generally manifested in a rise in national income The study will utilize GDP growth annually obtained from Macro trends site. (Xepapadeas, 2005). Ndavi (2012) used annual GDP statistics because it showed an overall picture of growth.

2.4 Empirical framework

Khondker, Bearish and Razzaque (2012) studied the effect of exchange rates on economic growth a case study of Bangladesh and they posit that devaluation of the domestic currency has been an important component of the primary stabilization program leading to trade policy reforms. By raising the domestic currency price of foreign exchange devaluation increases the price of traded goods relative to non-trade ones. Devaluations are believed to contribute to the enhancement of

external competitiveness stimulating production in the export sector. There are a number of theoretical reasons for a contractionary effect of devaluation. First it increases the price of traded goods, which feeds into the general price level rendering a negative balance effect. This in turn will result in lower aggregate demand and output. Second, the contractionary effect might also result from income distributional effect of devaluation.

Devaluation could lead to redistribution of income from people with high marginal propensity to consumption high propensity to save rendering a negative effect on the aggregate demand. Third, if the demand for imported goods is inelastic due to dominance of capital and essential intermediate and consumer. During the research done by Khondker, Berisha and Razzaque (2012) variable utilized were credit to the private sector, terms of trade, real exchange rate and real government expenditure. They used OLS to get the effect of real exchange rate on economic growth of Bangladesh, they carried out some diagnostic tests such as unit root testing and test for heteroskedasticity to ensure that the model was fit.

Objectives of the study included to examine the effect of real exchange rate movements on economic growth, to examine the effect of credit from the private sector on economic growth, to determine the effect of real government expenditure on economic growth and finally the effect of terms of trade on economic growth. Some of the findings in their research were that the movements in exchange rate do affect the overall output and the effect is borne out even after controlling for other variables. The study found out that long run effects of real devaluations are positive, in the short run the impact of devaluations is likely to be contractionary. The study concluded that real devaluations do have a positive effect on output or in other words economic growth (Khondker, Berisha and Razzaque (2012)).

Ndavi (2012) studies the effects of real exchange rate misalignment on economic growth. She used trade openness, Foreign aid, and inflation rate as her explanatory variables and uses Autoregressive Distributed Lag Model (ARDL) and Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) as her estimators. The study points out that the Kenyan economy relies on agriculture and tourism, which are dependent on the exchange rate, thus, the Kenyan economy is dependent on the exchange rate. The sustainability of economic growth relies on constantly growing exports hence trade openness is expected to have a positive impact on economic growth. Since the trade openness variable is positive, Kenya is an outward oriented economy which is advised for developing countries.

Trade openness gives access to imported capital goods and technological progress, this contributing to investment of both skill and innovation and competition, both within and outside Kenya. A large part of Kenya's foreign aid is used by the public sector, so that foreign aid contributes to the government expenditure (Ndavi 2012). In any economy, an increase in government expenditure leads to a decrease in economic growth. Kenya's aid being used for purposes such as financing the public sector rather than being used for development purposes and decreasing poverty-supplementing domestic sources of finance such as savings, has led to Kenya experiencing donor cuts (Ndavi 2012). The misappropriation of funds from the donor community has contributed negatively to economic growth in Kenya.

Inflation rate negatively affects economic growth in Kenya, although inflation rate is considered to be an insignificant variable. Inflation rate reduces investment as well as the efficiency of productive factors in any country hence it has a negative impact on economic growth. Ndavi concludes that the real exchange rate misalignment negatively affects economic growth in Kenya. This suggests that the Kenyan shilling is overvalued hence impacting economic growth negatively. Although there is no deterioration in external competitiveness as seen through trade openness, the

misallocation and misappropriation of domestic resources may be a factor. Another reason may be the fact that the exchange rate policies in Kenya are inappropriately formulated and implemented. (Ndavi 2012).

Akpan and Atan (2011) studied the effect of exchange rate movements on economic growth in Nigeria for the period 1986 to 2010 .their examine the possible direct and indirect relationship between exchange rates and GDP growth. The relationship is derived in two ways using a simultaneous equations model within a fully specified (but small) macroeconomic model .the study utilized Optimal currency area (OCA) theory, developed by Modell (1961) and McKinnon (1963). This literature focuses on trade, and stabilization of the business cycle. It is based on concepts of the symmetry of shocks, the degree of openness, and labor market mobility. According to the theory, a fixed exchange rate regime can increase trade and output growth by reducing exchange rate uncertainty and thus the cost of hedging, and also encourage investment by lowering currency premium from interest rates.

However, on the other hand it can also reduce trade and output growth by stopping, delaying or slowing the necessary relative price adjustment process. Variables used are money supply, exchange rate index, real output and rate of inflation. When doing the research Akpan and Atan (2011) used Estimation technique in determining the time series properties of data followed by co-integration test .thereafter, their performed system estimation using the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) procedure. Prior ,unit root test was performed on the series to determine their level of stationarity.The estimation results suggest that there is no evidence of a strong direct relationship between changes in exchange rate and output growth. (Akpan and Atan 2011). Also there is a statistically significant direct relationship between the two variables. The vector auto regression results also demonstrate that real exchange rate and real income are significantly co-

intergraded. In the long run, the exchange rate and income may drift apart, but in a short run their relationship is strong and direct. Given this, there is need to improve on the existing exchange rate management framework in Nigeria. Since this can influence the rate of income growth, but only in the context of a broad based economic reform involving a complementary monetary policy. Rather, Nigeria's economic growth has been directly affected by monetary variables. These factors tend to sustain a pattern of real exchange rate, which has been unfavorable for growth. Improvements in exchange rate management are necessary but not adequate to revive the Nigerian economy. A broad program of economic reform is required to complement the exchange rate policy adopted. (Akpan & Atan (2011)

Sibanda & Nwadi & Mlambo (2013) studied the effect impact of real exchange rate on economic growth. The study utilized variables such as real exchange rate, real interest rate, money supply, trade openness and gross fixed capital formulation. The model used in the study is the Johansen Cointegration vector error correction model. The study results showed that under devaluation of currency hampers economic growth in the long run. The study recommended that misalignment should be avoided at all costs.

Saungweme and Odhiambo (2021) studied the relationship between inflation and economic growth in Kenya from an analytical and empirical standpoint. Their used the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) bounds testing approach and the multivariate Granger-causality test using time series data covering (1970-2019). Structural breaks in the time series were also conducted using the Petron (1997) (PPURoot) and Zivot-Andrews (1992) (ZAU Root) techniques. Incorporating structural breaks into time series increases statistical inference's overall validity. Their found inflation and economic growth in Kenya to have structural breaks in 1995 and 1991. (Saungweme, 2012)

These years are marked by Kenya's economic, financial, public sector and institutional reforms. . The other findings of the study revealed that inflation has a statistically significant negative influence on long-term economic growth. Odhiambo, (2021) the multivariate Granger-causality results showed a distinct short-run unidirectional causality from economic growth to inflation in Kenya. In order to mitigate the negative consequences of inflation and the coronavirus on the economy and welfare, the study recommends that Kenya's government should pursue prudent monetary, financial, and fiscal policies to mitigate the negative effects of inflation and the covid-19 lockdown on the economy and welfare. Specifically, the country should implement an accommodative monetary policy, promote private sector creditor development, encourage stronger public sector investment, and keep inflation under control through rolling growth enhancing fiscal consolidation measures. (Saungweme, 2012)

2.5 Critique of the literature

On theoretical literature, it can be applauded that PPP exchange rates are relatively stable over time and by contrast market rates are more volatile and using them could be produce quite large swings in aggregate measures of growth. Despite this strength, the theory ignores many real determinants for example the theory saw a direct link between purchasing power and exchange rate however it ignores many factors of export and imports involved behind the operations (Taylor 2002)

On empirical, Ndavi (2012) studied the effects of real exchange rate misalignment on economic growth a case study of Kenya the scope of the study was excellent, it can be termed as valid and reliable. The extant literature although has various shortcomings the contextual characteristics of the country affect the results of the study for example misappropriation of foreign aid. The PPP approach of calculating real exchange rate misalignment does not provide a suitable estimate as it

does not allow for continuous changes in the economic fundamentals and microeconomic and trade policies.

Akpan and Atan (2011) is one of the studies on effects of exchange rate movements on economic growth. The study carried out in Nigeria examines the possible direct and indirect relationship between exchange rates and GDP growth. It helps provide a basis for comparison for other developing countries which are facing the same challenge with exchange rate policy effects on economic growth. However, it has some shortcomings. For instance, it only focuses on Nigeria's economy and its overdependence on imports which have direct negative effects on exchange rates and fail to incorporate other sectors of the economy that also affect economic growth like the level of development in Nigeria's economy.

It has also been limited to Nigeria's economy and fails to incorporate other exchange rate markets outside Nigeria which would provide a better perspective. According to Sibanda & Nwadi & Mlambo (2013), real devaluations do have a negative impact on economic growth. On inflation, Saungweme and Odhiambo (2021) studied the effect of inflation on economic growth where the study concluded that inflation affects economic growth negatively in the short run and that it has no effect in the long run at all. The shortcoming is on why the study believes that inflation only affects economic growth in the short run and does not have any effect in the long run.

2.6 Research Gap

Following the literature review in the foregoing sections, the research gap in this study is the evidence gap. This is a contradictory evidence gap in that there are contradicting information in that studies have arrived at different conclusions. Khondker, Bearish and Razzaque (2012) concluded that real devaluations have a positive effect on output or in other words economic growth while

Ndavi 2012 in his study concluded that real devaluations have negative effect on output or in other words economic growth although the studies had different case studies in that one is based on Bangladesh and one is based on a case study of Kenya. The present study intends to fill this gap by analyzing the Kenyan data obtained from Central Bank of Kenya Website from the year 2006 to 2021. In this study we intend to investigate whether inflation, trade openness, foreign direct investment and exchange rates have positive or negative impact on economic growth.

2.7 Summary

This section summarizes the theoretical, conceptual, and empirical framework. Theories that explain the relationship between exchange rate and economic growth are two that is purchasing power parity theory and the International Fisher Effect (IFE). Purchasing power parity theory is categorized into two that is absolute purchasing power parity and relative purchasing power parity. The absolute purchasing power parity theory postulate that the equilibrium exchange rate between currencies of two countries is equal to the ratio of the price level in the two nations. This means that the price of two similar products of two different countries should be equal when measured in a common currency.

The relative PPP theory on the other hand is an alternative version which postulates that the change in the exchange rate over a period of time should be proportional to the relative change in the price levels in the two nations over the same period. The two measures the impact of exchange rate on economic growth. The IFE theory uses interest rates rather than inflation to explain the changes in exchange rate overtime and the impact on economic growth. The IFE suggests that given two countries the country with the higher interest rate will depreciate by the amount of the interest rate differential.

Conceptual framework shows the interrelationship between the variables and in this case the independent variables are exchange rates, inflation rate, trade openness and foreign direct investment all affect economic growth which is the dependent variable.

There are many studies that have been made for example Khondker, Berisha and Razzaque (2012) carried out a study on the effect of exchange rate on economic growth a case study of Bangladesh where they found out that real devaluations do have a positive effect on output or in other words economic growth. Another study done by Ndavi (2012), studied the effect of real exchange rate misalignment on economic growth where she concluded that the real exchange rate negatively affects economic growth in Kenya. Akpan and Atan (2011) studied the effects of exchange rate movement on the economic growth of Nigeria where they concluded that there is statistically significant direct relationship between the two variables in the short run the relationship is strong and direct.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This chapter provides the bases of testing the research hypotheses of the study and provides the mechanisms for achieving the study objectives. It not only provides the study design but also defines the study population and sampling technique. It ultimately sheds light of the study model, the descriptive statistic and the test of hypotheses proposed for the study.

3.2 Research design

The research design refers to the framework of research methods and techniques chosen by a research and in this case, the study uses descriptive design. It is an arrangement of conditions for collection and analysis of data in a manner to combine relevance to the research. The main objective is to improve the research findings validity by removing potential sources of bias that could skew the results. This study is designed as research of the value of exchange rates of Kenya over a period of 28 years, spanning 1993 through 2021. According to Khondker, Berisha and Razzaque (2012), a study is suitable when observation is to be repeatedly made on the same subject over a long period of time. In this study, exchange rates and economic growth values of Kenya will be collected and analyzed over a 28-year period, covering 1993-2021.

3.3 Study Population

This section is basically about total number of observations that can be obtained. The population is the collection of individual details in that study. The study population consists of values of exchange rate and economic growth retrieved from the Central Bank of Kenya, World Bank, CEIC data and macrotrends as at 13th November, 2022 (this research utilizes secondary data). The study covers up to 2021.

3.4 Sample and Sample Design

This section basically shows the approach used selecting the study units from the population. Sampling means selecting the group that you will actually collect data from when conducting a research (Thompson, 2012). It can also be termed as the process of selecting a sample from a statistical population in order to estimate characteristics of the entire population. Sampling is the process of picking an appropriate sample or a representative subset of a population in order to determine parameters or characteristics of the entire population (Thompson, 2012). Purposive sampling also known as judge mental sampling a non-probability sampling technique where the researcher at their own discretion chooses variables for the sample population.

3.4.1 Sampling frame

According to Thompson (2012) sampling frame is a researcher's device to specify the population of interest. It is a source material from which a sample is drawn. Sampling frame is exchange rate values from 1992 to 2021 retrieved from The Central Bank site.

3.4.2 Sampling size

The sampling size according to Thompson (2012) is a term used by researchers to means number of observations used for determining the estimations of a given population. The study is designed

to utilize exchange rate and economic growth data from 2006 to 2021, a case study of Kenya, as at 13th November, 2022.

3.5 Data and Data Collection

This section details the data used in the study and how it is collected

3.5.1 Research Data

Secondary data is used in the study to evaluate the effects of exchange rate to economic growth. The data will be obtained from monthly exchange rates (period average) at the Central Bank site. The data on inflation, trade openness and FDI will be obtained from the CEIC data site. The data will be used to measure the effects of exchange rate on economic growth.

3.5.2 Data Collection Instruments

Data collection is the systematic measurement and gathering of information on particular variables of interest in order to test hypotheses, answer research questions and assess outcomes (original et al,2018).the study will rely on secondary data

3.6 Data Analysis and Presentation

This section provides the approach that is expected to be used to analyze research data. It provides measures of the variables as well as test statistics to be used in testing the hypotheses to evaluate the effects of exchange rate on the economic growth of Kenya.

3.6.1 Model Specification

The model to be used in the analysis is a multiple linear regression which shows the relationship between variables. The theoretical model represents a long run relationship between aggregate output and a number of other variables like exchange rate, inflation, trade openness and foreign direct investments. In this study economic growth is the dependent variable while inflation, foreign

direct investment and trade openness form the independent variables. The econometric model is given below:

$$\ln(EG_t) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln(ER) + \beta_2 \ln(FDI_t) + \beta_3 \ln(IT) + \beta_4 \ln(TO_t) + \epsilon_t$$

Where;

EG= Economic growth

ER= Exchange rate

FDI= Foreign direct investment

IT= inflation

TO= trade openness

ϵ_t = stochastic error term

Where $\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4$ are the respective estimators

In the model, the objective is to test the statistical significance of β_1 , the coefficient of exchange rate. The regression analysis will be run three times each of the various indicators of economic growth. B_0 is the model constant while β_1 is the coefficient of the exchange rate which is to be tested for statistical significance at 95% confidence interval to find out if exchange rate affects economic growth and the nature of the effect if it is negative or positive effect.

3.6.2 Variable operationalization.

To measure the variables, the proxies indicated in table 3.1 will be used.

Variable	Indicators	type	source	Measure
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Economic growth	GDP	dependent	Central bank site	LnEG
Exchange rates	Exchange rate	independent	Central bank site	LnER
Foreign direct investment	Receipts from foreign direct investment	Independent	CEIC data site	LnFDI
Inflation	Consumer price index	independent	World Bank site	LnIT

CEIC data is an acronym for computer and enterprise investigations conference.

3.6.3 Diagnostic tests

The diagnostic tests will include normality test using kurtosis and skewness values, multicollinearity test using Eigen value VIF and conditional index and correlation correlation analysis. For the overall model, the coefficient of determination (r-square) will be used to show the overall explanatory power of exchange rates, inflation, FDI, and trade openness on economic growth. F test is used to show the goodness of fit of the model. It would be considered a good fit if the f ratio from regression output would be greater than the critical level of significance.

Tests for autocorrelation will be done using the Durbin Watson test. This study also runs a test for multicollinerity test using Eigenvalue test.

3.6.4 Descriptive statistical test

This study runs descriptive tests such as mean, median, kurtosis, range value which will help give the general description of the independent variables and the dependent variable.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESEARCH FINDINGS, PRESENTATION AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Introduction

The chapter comprises of descriptive summary results together with test for assumptions under the correlation analysis, regression analysis, diagnostic tests and most importantly a discussion of the study results.

4.2 Descriptive statistical test findings

This section will present descriptive statistical findings that consists of the standard deviation, the mean, the maximum and minimum values, skewness, kurtosis and the number of observations and they are displayed below in table 4.1.

Table 4.1 Descriptive statistical findings

	EXCHANGE RATE	INFLATION RATE	FDI	GDPGROWTH
N Valid	29	29	29	29
Missing	1	1	1	1
Mean	314.7315	32.4667	3.0697	3.8262
Std. Error of Mean	39.18568	4.46515	.52008	.42013
Median	327.2685	28.7726	3.8000	4.1500
Mode	-26.61 ^a	-1.35 ^a	.01 ^a	-.25 ^a
Std. Deviation	211.02132	24.04557	2.80072	2.26245
Variance	44529.999	578.189	7.844	5.119
Skewness	.190	.819	.103	-.236
Std. Error of Skewness	.434	.434	.434	.434
Kurtosis	-.307	.207	-1.513	-.597
Std. Error of Kurtosis	.845	.845	.845	.845
Range	851.09	94.84	8.31	8.31

Minimum	-26.61	-1.35	-.25	-.25
Maximum	824.47	93.49	8.06	8.06
Sum	9127.21	941.54	89.02	110.96

the table above present the descriptive statistical findings where the mean of GDP is 3.8262, maximum 8.06, minimum -0.25, the mean of exchange rate is 314.7315, maximum 824.47, minimum -26.61, inflation mean is 32.4667, maximum 93.49, minimum -1.35 and the last variable foreign direct investment mean 3.0697, maximum 8.06, minimum -0.25. The findings also showed that the standard deviation of GDP being 2.26245, exchange rate being 211.02132, inflation being 24.04557 and foreign direct investment being 2.80072. Following the findings of the study the skewness of the study is -0.236, exchange rate 0.190, inflation 0.819 and FDI 0.103. the values for the kurtosis for GDP -0.597, exchange rate -0.307, inflation 0.207 and FDI -1.513 which shows that the data is normally distributed with the range -0.236 and 0.819 which means that there are no outliers in the data. 4.4 Inferential statistical test findings

4.4.3 Diagnostic tests

From the above the results of the skewness of all variables under the study that is:

4.4.3.1 Normality test

Table 4.2 Skewness and kurtosis

	Exchange	Inflation	FDI	GDP growth rate
Skewness	.190	.819	.103	-.236
Std. Error of Skewness	.434	.434	.434	.434
Kurtosis	-.307	.207	-1.513	-.597
Std. Error of Kurtosis	.845	.845	.845	.845

Skewness is a measurement of the distortion of symmetrical distribution or asymmetry in a data set. It is basically the degree of asymmetry observed in a probability distribution. If the skewness is between -0.5 and 0.5, then the data is fairly symmetrical. If the skewness is between -1 and -0.5 or between 0.5 and 1, then the data is moderately skewed. If the skewness is less than -1 or greater than 1, the data is highly skewed. Kurtosis is a measure of the tailedness of a distribution. Tailedness is how often outliers occur. Excess kurtosis is the tailedness of a distribution relative to a normal distribution. Distributions with medium kurtosis are mesokurtic and distributions with low kurtosis are platykurtic. If the kurtosis is greater than 3, then the dataset has heavier tails than a normal distribution. If the kurtosis is less than 3, then the dataset has lighter tails than a normal distribution.

The dependent and independent ranges is between -1 and 1 which shows that the data is normally distributed.

4.4.3.2 Multicollinearity test

Table 4.3 Collinearity Diagnostics

Mode	Dime	Eigenv	Condi	Variance Proportions			
1	nsion	alue	tion	(const	Exchange	Inflation	FDI
	1	3.518	1.000	.01	.00	.02	.01
	2	.276	3.569	.49	.01	.01	.09
1	3	.174	4.502	.16	.04	.94	.01
	4	.032	10.47	.34	.95	.04	.90

a. Dependent Variable: GDPGROWTH

Eigenvalues are the special set of scalar values that is associated with the set of linear equations most probably in the matrix equations. Eigen' is a German word that means 'proper' or 'characteristic'. Therefore, the term eigenvalue can be termed as characteristic value, characteristic root, proper values or latent roots as well. According to Slinker and Glantz (1985) Eigen value of more than 10 indicates harmful multicollinearity. From the above table the eigenvalues are all less than 10 indicating that there is absence of multicollinearity. According to Hae 2019, the largest condition index is called the condition number. A condition number between 10 and 30 indicates the presence of multicollinearity (Hae 2019). From the results above the condition index do not range between 10 and 30 hence absence of multicollinearity. Variance inflation factor (VIF), measures the correlation and strength of correlation between the predictor variables in a regression model (Noora 2020). According to Noora (2020) VIF of 0.80 or higher indicates presence of multicollinearity. From the above results, the variance inflation factor are all less than 0.80 hence absence of multicollinearity.

4.4.4.3 Correlation analysis

Table 4.4 shows the results of correlation analysis that shows the strength of the correlation among the study factors.

Table 4.4 Correlation analysis

		GDPGROWTH	Exchange	Inflation	FDI
Kendall's tau_b	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.953**	-.5570**	.749**
	GDPGROWTH Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000	.000	.000
	N	29	29	29	29
	Correlation Coefficient	.953**	1.000	.498**	.690**
	Exchange rate Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.	.000	.000
	N	29	29	29	29
	Correlation Coefficient	-.557**	.498**	1.000	.507**
	Inflation Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.	.000
	N	29	29	29	29
	Correlation Coefficient	.749**	.690**	.507**	1.000
	FDI Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.
	N	29	29	29	29
Spearman's rho	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.942**	-.650**	.484**
	GDPGROWTH Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000	.000	.000
	N	29	29	29	29
	Correlation Coefficient	.942*	1.000	.653**	.871**
	Exchange rate Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.	.000	.000
	N	29	29	29	29
	Correlation Coefficient	-.650**	.653**	1.000	.645**
	Inflation rate Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.	.000
	N	29	29	29	29
	Correlation Coefficient	.484**	.871**	.645**	1.000
	FDI Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.
	N	29	29	29	29

The study employed two methods of correlation analysis that is Kendall's tau b correlation and Spearman correlation. The Kendall tau-b correlation coefficient, is a nonparametric measure of association based on the number of concordances and discordances in paired observations (Roger 2002). Spearman rank correlation is a non-parametric test that is used to measure the degree of association between two variables (Wanga & Shepherd 2018). The results of the study shows that with Kendall's tau correlation the association between GDP and exchange rate is strong positive (0.953) and is significant since the p value is 0.000, the association between GDP and inflation is strong negative (-0.557) and is significant since the p value is 0.000, the association between GDP and FDI is strong and positive (0.749) and is significant with a p value of 0.000. The association between exchange rate and inflation weakly positive (0.4980 with a p value of 0.000, the association between exchange rate and FDI is strong positive (0.690) with a p value of 0.000. the association between inflation and FDI is fairly positive 0.507 and significant.

From the results, the spearman rank correlation that shows relation between GDP and exchange rate is strong and positive 0.942 and is significant, GDP and inflation is strong and negative (-0.650) and is significant, the association between GDP and FDI is fairly positive (0.484) and is significant, the relation between exchange rate and inflation is strong and positive (0.653) and is significant, the association between exchange rate and FDI is strong and positive (0.871) and finally the association between inflation and FDI is strongly positive 0.645 and significant at a p value of 0.000.

Table 4.5 Model summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
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1	.957 ^a	.916	.906	.69499
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The model summary results on table above indicates that R square is 0.916 which essentially means that predictors account for 91.6% of the changes in the dependent variable which in this case is GDP growth rate. The remaining 8.4 % is explained by the variables not considered in the research and the error term. The Durbin Watson statistics of 1.713 which lies between the 1.5 and 2.5 which means that there is no autocorrelation among the research variables.

4.4.1.2.2 Anova analysis

ANOVA is a statistical formula used to compare variances across the means of different groups. The outcome of ANOVA is the 'F statistic'. It shows the difference between the within group variance and the between group variance, which produces a figure which allows a conclusion that the null hypothesis is supported or rejected. The null hypothesis is rejected when there is a significant difference between the groups, as the F ratio will be larger.

Kazerouni (2009)

Table 4.6 Anova table

ANOVA						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
	Regression	131.248	3	43.749	90.577	.000 ^b
1	Residual	12.075	25	.483		
	Total	143.323	28			

The above table indicates that the analysis of variance which shows that the regression model is important in showing the relationship among the study variables. The displayed F statistic is 90.577 which is significant at 95 % level of significance the p value is 0.0000

4.4.1.3 Regression coefficients.

Table 4.7

Model	Unstandardized		Standardized	t	Sig.	
	Coefficients B	Std. Error	Coefficients Beta			
	(Constant)	.360	.272		1.323	.198
1	Exchange rate	.009	.001	.886	6.498	.000
	Inflation rate	-.019	.007	.206	2.832	.009
	FDI	.049	.116	-.061	-.426	.674

Dependent Variable: GDPGROWTH.

The results on table 4.7 show that the regression model is:

$GDP = 0.360 + 0.09 \text{ exchange rate} - 0.019 \text{ inflation rate} + 0.49 \text{ foreign direct investments}$

If the exchange rate increases by 1 unit, all other factors remaining constant, the GDP will increase by 0.09 units. If the inflation rate decreases by one unit, all other factors remaining constant, the GDP increases by 0.019 units. If the foreign direct investments increase by 1 unit, all other factors remaining constant, the GDP will increase by 0.49 units. From the regression equation, the findings reveal that there is a statistically significant positive relationship between exchange rates and GDP, statistically significant negative relationship between GDP and

inflation and a statistically significant positive relationship between GDP and foreign direct investments.

4.6 Discussion of the findings.

4.6.1 Discussion on exchange rate

The findings show that a statistically significant link exists between GDP and exchange rate. This relationship is positive and that it has a considerable impact on economic growth so it is significant in determining the output of Kenya, the coefficient as indicated above is statistically significant. The result confirms what is normally expected that real exchange rate depreciation or devaluation comes with an increase in economic growth. The study agrees with a study done by Econstor (2010) that real devaluations have a positive effect on economic growth. Econstor (2010) conducted a research to investigate the relationship between exchange rate and economic growth as well as the relationship between inflation and economic growth.

Ndavi (2012) investigated the effect of real exchange rate misalignment on economic growth where the study concluded that it does have a negative impact on economic growth which suggests that Kenyan shilling is overvalued hence impacting economic growth negatively. According to Sibanda & Ncwadi & Mlambo (2013) real devaluations do have a negative impact on economic growth this study contradicts this evidence. Their study indicated that undervaluation of the currency significantly hampers growth negatively and as such the policy of depreciating exchange rate to achieve higher growth rate is not sustainable in the long run.

They recommended that misalignment of the currency should be avoided at all costs. The study has now filled this gap of contradictory evidence by the findings indicate a positive effect of real devaluations on economic growth. The case study was on South Africa which might

have different conditions with Kenya. Another study by Ndungu (2013) also discovered that exchange rate devaluations does negatively affect economic growth.

4.6.2 Discussion on Inflation

The findings on inflation indicate that a statistically significant link exists between GDP and inflation. The relationship is negative and has a considerable impact on economic growth. The coefficient is indicated to be significant due to the p value being 0.0000. (Odhiambo 2021) notes that inflation does positively affect economic growth but up to a certain point very high inflation rates does hamper economic growth. This study confirms what Odhiambo (2021) found out in the research of effect of inflation on economic growth. Kasidi (2011) also conducted a study of effect of inflation in economic growth where the results showed that inflation has a negative impact on economic growth but no cointegration between inflation and economic during the period of the study and concluded that there is no long run relationship between inflation and economic growth.

4.6.3 Discussion on FDI

With regards to foreign direct investment the findings indicate that a statistically significant link exists between foreign direct investment and GDP. The relationship is positive and has a significant impact on economic growth. Hlavacek & Bal-Domanska (2016) sought to analyse FDI and its impact on economic growth in the Central and Southern European countries where they found out that increase of FDI positively demonstrates itself in increasing the level of GDP. The influence of FDI on economic growth of the Central and Eastern European countries was more visible in the period 2009 to 2012. According to Borensztein & Gregorio & Lee FDI is an important vehicle for the transfer of technology contributing relatively more to the

growth than the domestic investment however, the productivity only holds when the host country has a minimum threshold stock of human capital. This study also agrees with Nyaga (2013) that foreign direct investment does have a positive impact on economic growth.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.0 Introduction

This chapter consists of the study summary, research according to the results of the study and recommendations and the conclusion. This chapter also shows an area for further study.

5.1 Summary

The goal of the research was to figure out how exchange rate affects economic growth a case study of Kenya. The objective of the study was to examine the effect of exchange rate fluctuations on economic growth, to determine the effect of FDI on economic growth and to determine the effect of inflation rate on economic growth. The scope of the study covered the question of interest was whether exchange rate do have a significant effect on economic growth. International Fisher Effect Theory (1930), relative and absolute Purchasing Power parity (1919) provided the theoretical literature review on exchange rate while market power theory, conventional demand pull inflation and structural theory of inflation formed the theoretical literature review on inflation. The study utilized a descriptive research design with annually secondary data over 28 year period (1993-2021) and to summarize the data descriptive statistics such as mean, standard deviation, maximum and minimum values and variance. In addition the study used correlation and multivariate regression to examine the strength of the association between the variables under investigation.

The descriptive results found out GDP had a mean value of 3.262, exchange rate 314.7315, inflation rate 32.4667 and FDI 3.0697. Skewness for the data was -0.236 for GDP, 0.190, inflation rate 0.819 and FDI 0.103 while kurtosis for GDP -.597, exchange rate -0.307, inflation rate 0.207 and FDI -1.513 which shows that the data was normally distributed hence model is fit. The regression analysis revealed that 90.6 % of the changes in GDP is explained by the explanatory variables that is exchange rate, inflation rate and foreign direct investment. The results also showed that the model was fit with a p value of 0.0000 which means it is fit to forecast the study. The coefficient results showed a positive correlation between GDP and exchange rate, negative between GDP and inflation and a positive correlation between FDI and GDP. Further, the relationship results revealed a positive and strong positive relationship between exchange rate and economic growth, relationship between inflation and economic growth where it revealed to be strong negative (-0.65). The relationship between FDI and economic growth revealed to be a fair positive relationship (0.484). The coefficients for the predictors were individually significant because of p value of 0.000 for each of the predictors.

5.2 Conclusion

5.2.1 Conclusion based on exchange rate objective

The study adduced evidence that the exchange rate does have a positive impact on economic growth. There is a statistically significant direct relationship between exchange rate and economic growth. How movements in the exchange rate affect overall economic activity has been a subject of longstanding controversy in macroeconomics and empirical scrutiny in applied policy analysis. In Kenya the news of depreciation is mostly greeted with skepticism about macroeconomic soundness of the economy, triggering public and policy debates. The issue is certainly controversial as exporters often demand for downward adjustments of the

domestic currency in order to become more competitive in international markets in sharp contrast to protests by consumers and others who rely on imported goods for consumption and production and the increased value of dollar (or other foreign currencies for that matter) get translated into their higher prices. In recent times when the country has witnessed a general rise in prices, currency depreciation is widely regarded as a wrong policy choice contributing to the inflationary pressure. Kenya officially maintains a floating exchange rate policy which would imply that in the face of a deteriorating external balance downward adjustment becomes inevitable. While the discussions on devaluations focus mainly on inflation, growth implications are rarely given adequate attention. In theory, currency depreciation is associated with possibilities for both contractionary and expansionary effects on outputs of different sectors. This would imply that for any country the net impact has to be determined empirically. Experiences of different countries and regions - as demonstrated in different studies - differ, further illustrating the need for undertaking country-specific empirical analysis. This paper has made an attempt to examine the effects of exchange rate changes on Kenyan aggregate output, measured by GDP.

In this study it can be concluded that real devaluations are found to be positive that is downward adjustment essentially has an expansionary effect in the long run but in the short run it has a contractionary effect. Similarly, the appreciation of the real exchange rate will have adverse consequences for overall economic output.

5.2.2 Conclusion based on inflation objective

It can be noted that increase in inflation is accompanied by a decline in the purchasing power of money which reduces consumption and therefore GDP decreases. High inflation can make investment less desirable since it creates uncertainty for the future and it can affect the balance

of payments as exports become more expensive. It can be concluded therefore, that inflation does have a negative relationship hence negative impact generally but bits of inflation does have a positive effect on economic growth.

5.2.3 Conclusion based on FDI objective

Inward investment leads to high productivity growth, through an increased availability of capital hence resulting to competition. Productivity is a key factor that increases the country's competitiveness abroad and raises the living standards at home country. Finally FDI does have a positive effect on economic growth

5.3 Recommendations

5.3.1 Recommendations based on exchange rate

With the results above, Kenyan government should focus on implementing monetary trade policy that suit the Kenyan economy appropriately. Exchange rate policies should also be revised to makes sure they are of maximum positive value to the economy. Suitable exchange rate policy may decrease the overvaluation of the Kenyan Shilling and this will eventually result in proper allocation of resources. Exchange rate should be managed more vigorously as this contributes well to economic growth. It needs to be pointed out that the ability to maintain a depreciated real exchange rate regime is going to be far more challenging than staging nominal devaluations. The government can promote export-oriented growth: A competitive exchange rate can make exports more affordable and increase demand for domestically produced goods and services, which can boost economic growth. Policies that promote exports, such as export subsidies and tax incentives, can also be helpful.

5.3.2 Recommendations on inflation

The government can tightening Monetary Policy The Central Bank of Kenya can use monetary policy tools such as raising interest rates, increasing the reserve requirement for banks, and reducing the money supply to curb inflation. Another recommendation is on Fiscal Measures, The Kenyan government can adopt fiscal measures such as reducing public spending, increasing taxes, and cutting subsidies to reduce demand and control inflation. Addressing Supply-Side Issues can help maintain the inflation rate, the government can address supply-side issues such as improving infrastructure, reducing trade barriers, and encouraging investment in key sectors to boost productivity and supply and reduce the cost of goods and services another recommendation is on controlling Food Prices, Food prices have a significant impact on inflation in Kenya. The government can control food prices by reducing post-harvest losses, promoting irrigation and other agricultural technologies, and reducing inefficiencies in the food supply chain. Promoting Competition will come in handy in that, encouraging competition in markets can help to reduce prices and inflation. The government can reduce barriers to entry, encourage new businesses to enter markets, and promote fair competition. Addressing External Factors will also help curb inflation the Kenyan government can also address external factors such as global oil prices and exchange rate fluctuations. The government can reduce the impact of these factors by diversifying the economy and strengthening the country's export base.

5.3.3 Recommendations on FDI

Some of the recommendations on FDI may be to improve infrastructure: A country's infrastructure plays a crucial role in attracting foreign investment. Governments should focus on building and upgrading transportation, communication, and energy infrastructure to make their country an attractive destination for FDI. The government can also reduce bureaucratic red tape. Excessive

regulations and bureaucracy can deter foreign investors from entering a country. Governments should streamline their processes for starting and operating a business to reduce the time and cost associated with investing in their country. Finally the government can provide incentives. Governments can offer tax breaks, subsidies, and other incentives to foreign investors to encourage them to invest in their country. These incentives should be carefully targeted to ensure they are effective in attracting the right kind of investment. The utilization of FDI appropriately may also contribute to economic growth and a competitive currency, as impactful trade policies be put in place.

5.4 Areas for Further study

The study suggested a few areas for further study which includes the following:

- Big data analysis can help predict economic growth in the long run hence can government to come up with specific policies for the purpose of economic growth
- Another case for a further study why inflation does not affect economic growth in the long run. The study could state why this is the case.
- Trade flows: The impact of exchange rates on trade flows is an important area to study. Specifically, it is important to examine how changes in exchange rates affect the volume and composition of imports and exports, as this can have a significant impact on economic growth.
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